

A Kinetic Study of the Effect of Aquo-Ethylene Glycol on Hydrolysis of Ethyl Picolinate

D. K. VERMA^{*a}, BHAGWANJI SINGH^b and RAM PRAVESH SINGH^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Patna University-800 005

^bDepartment of Chemistry, S. S. College, Aurangabad-824 101

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The study of the solvent effect of the protic solvent on the hydrolysis of carboxylic acid esters has been carried out by a number of workers¹, but very little attempt has been made so far on heterocyclic acid esters. Moreover, the explanations put forward are also not quite satisfactory.

As the usual titrimetric method can not be employed for knowing the rate measurement of the reactions, the study of these heterocyclic acid esters becomes interesting. Hence, an attempt has been made on a kinetic study of the effect of aqueous ethylene glycol-water media on the hydrolysis of ethyl picolinate.

in accordance with the prediction of Hughes and Ingold². In the plot of $\log k$ against mole percent of the solvent, the decrease appears to be quite gradual. The hydrolysis reaction was found to obey the Arrhenius law throughout the range of temperature and composition under study. The E_c values (kcal mol^{-1}) calculated from the plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ are as follows (% solvent in parenthesis): (10%) 12.59, (20%) 11.26, (30%) 10.44, (40%) 9.58, (50%) 9.26. The E_c values decrease with increasing proportion of organic co-solvent in the solvent mixture. The decrease in E_c values can result due to the following two alternatives: (i) the transition state is more solvated than the initial state, and (ii) the initial state is more desolvated than the transition state. But the ΔS^* value shows decreasing trend (Table 2) with increasing proportion of organic co-solvent which indicates that the transition state is more stabilised

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT (k , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D) VALUES FOR ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYL PICOLINATE IN ETHYLENE GLYCOL-WATER MEDIUM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Solvent %		25°	30°	35°	45°
10	D	75.25	73.50	71.25	68.00
	k	20.89	28.84	38.90	74.13
20	D	72.25	70.50	68.75	65.50
	k	16.98	22.39	30.20	53.70
30	D	69.25	67.50	65.75	62.50
	k	14.13	18.20	23.99	40.74
40	D	65.75	64.00	62.50	59.25
	k	12.02	15.49	19.95	32.36
50	D	62.25	60.50	58.75	55.75
	k	10.47	13.18	16.60	26.30

Results and Discussion

The specific rate constant values (Table 1) have been found to decrease with increasing proportion of organic co-solvent in the solvent mixture

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN AQUO-ETHYLENE GLYCOL MIXTURE

Temp. °C		Solvent %				
		10	20	30	40	50
25	ΔH^*	11.82	10.86	9.85	9.58	8.84
	ΔG^*	18.09	18.21	18.32	18.42	18.50
	ΔS^*	21.04	24.67	28.43	29.66	32.40
30	ΔG^*	18.19	18.33	18.46	18.56	18.67
	ΔS^*	21.05	24.66	28.43	29.65	32.43
	ΔG^*	18.32	18.47	18.61	18.72	18.83
35	ΔS^*	21.10	24.72	28.45	29.69	32.46
	ΔG^*	18.52	18.73	18.90	19.04	19.18
	ΔS^*	21.08	24.74	28.47	29.76	32.50

ΔH^* , ΔG^* in kcal mol^{-1} ; ΔS^* in $\text{cal K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$

than the initial state. Hence, alternative (i) is the suitable probability which can be applied in the present case. This seems to be the reason of the decrease in rate constant in spite of decrease in the activation energy.

The ΔG^* value increases as the proportion of ethylene glycol is increased. This shows that the stability of transition is very little affected by the addition of organic co-solvent.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of C.P. (Merck) grade. Ethylene glycol was purified by known procedure. Water used was double-distilled conductivity water. Conductance was measured with an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge. In the present hydrolysis, the faster hydroxyl ions are replaced by slow picolinate ions resulting in progressive decrease in the conductance of the reaction mixture. The rate constant was determined by suitably correlating the conductance of the reaction mixture with the concentration of the reactants. A 0.05 N solution of the ester and a 0.05 N NaOH solution were

used. The rate constant values were evaluated from the equation,

$$\Delta t = \Delta_{\infty} + \frac{1}{ak} \frac{\Delta_0 - \Delta_t}{t}$$

where, Δ_0 is the initial conductivity before addition of ester to the alkali, Δ_t the conductivity at time, t (min), Δ_{∞} the conductivity when the ester is completely hydrolysed, a the mole concentration of the alkali, and k the rate constant value was calculated from the slope of the plot Δ_t against $(\Delta_0 - \Delta_t)/t$.

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